

The Effect of Telehealth Diabetes Self-Management Education and Support Classes on Diabetic Glycemic Control

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Background

- 7.3 million people, or 11.3% of the US population affected by diabetes mellitus (DM)¹
- Uncontrolled DM leads to increased morbidity and mortality^{2,3}
- Annual healthcare expenditure for one person with DM is estimated at \$16,752, more than 2x the costs for someone without DM^{1,4}
- DSMES classes effectively improve glycemic control with minimal adverse effects^{2,5,6,7,8,9}
- A 1% decrease in HgbA1C reduces the risk of serious complications by 45% and up to 13% reduction in cost^{10,11}
- Lev Vygotsky's Collaborative Learning Theory supports interactive socialization as a key factor in internalizing new knowledge^{12,13}

Purpose

To evaluate the effect of interactive telehealth Diabetes Self-Management and Education Support (DSMES) classes on glycemic control amongst adults with uncontrolled DM type 2 (DMT2).

Methods

Setting: Outpatient community clinic

Inclusion Criteria: Diagnosis of DMT2, HgbA1C ≥ 9.0 , ages 18 to 74, access to an electronic device with sound and video capabilities, English or Spanish speaking

Exclusion Criteria: diabetes mellitus type 1, prediabetes, hemodialysis status, gestational diabetes, cognitive delays

Sample: A convenience sample

Measures: HgbA1C pre & post-intervention, Diabetes Knowledge Questionnaire (DKQ), participant-generated blood glucose levels, and satisfaction survey.

Intervention: Participants attended a one-hour interactive online classroom once a week for 5 weeks. The National Standards guided the bilingual English and Spanish courses for DSMES. The class facilitator encouraged interaction and collaborative problem-solving throughout each session to help the participants internalize concepts.

Conceptual Framework

Lev Vygotsky's Collaborative Learning Theory

The Model for Improvement and PDSA Cycle

Limitations

- Limited sample size (n = 9)
- Inconsistent attendance to classes
- A low number of submissions for satisfaction surveys and self-generated blood glucose logs.
- Limitations in data analysis due to Pre-and Post-intervention diabetes health literacy per participant could not be matched.
- No control group to compare

Conclusions

- Telehealth DSMES classes can offer improvement in glycemic control for adults with uncontrolled DMT2
- Participants reported overall satisfaction with the online remote-learning format.
- Class scheduling demonstrated as a barrier to participation.
- Participants need assistance with independently accessing and completing online surveys.
- Nursing professionals are in the ideal position to lead DSMES classes and offer ongoing patient support in the outpatient sector.

Recommendations

- Provide class times that accommodate the patients' schedules to increase access.
- Attach patient identifiers to online survey responses to better analyze the effect of DSMES classes on health literacy and satisfaction.
- Designate time during class sessions to complete online surveys. Offer real-time technical support.
- Provide monolingual sessions to eliminate barriers with language translation.

References

Results

Sample Demographics:

- 9 adults with DMT2 and HgbA1C $\geq 9.0\%$
- 3 English-speaking, 6 Spanish-speaking
- 9 female, 0 male
- Mean age 52.44 years

- Mann-Whitney U Test $p = .142$
- 1.6% reduction in median HgbA1C post-DSMES

Diabetes health literacy was greater during course participation.

Note. CL = center line, LCL = lower control limit, UCL = upper control limit

- The mean BG pre-intervention was 290.7 mg/dL, reduced to mean BG 154.9 mg/dL post-intervention.
- Control Chart X-bar S analysis reveals a process change after the implementation of DSMES classes.

Satisfaction scores remained high, ranging 4.40 to 5.0 on a 5-point Likert scale.